

Analysis of Spiritual-Enlightenmental Activity in New Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *In this article, the role of spiritual and educational initiatives carried out in our country in modern society, youth education and preservation of national values, educational actions, activities carried out by state programs and public organizations are considered. Revolutionary changes in the fields of culture, art and education, which are important in the development of spirituality, are also analyzed. As a result, conclusions are drawn about the spiritual and educational prospects of Uzbekistan and the directions of further development.*

Keywords: *New Uzbekistan, spiritual and educational activities, youth, spirituality, national culture, value, Renaissance, national identity, society, humanism, transformational processes.*

Uzbekistan, known for its rich culture and historical heritage, pays great attention to the development of spiritual and educational activities. This activity is important not only in increasing the spiritual potential of the people, but also in educating the young generation.

The main directions of spiritual and educational activities:

Education and Training: The education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is mainly aimed at imparting moral values to the younger generation. Programs providing spiritual education are being developed in schools, universities and other educational institutions. National culture and traditions, religious education and moral values take a special place in the educational process.

Culture and art: Uzbekistan is actively developing spiritual and educational activities in the fields of art and culture. The cultural heritage, customs and traditions of our people are promoted through concerts, theatrical productions, exhibitions and cultural events. These events also help to form the cultural brand of Uzbekistan at the international level.

Religious activity: Religious values also play an important role in spiritual education in Uzbekistan. Islam is the main religion of the country's population. Religion plays an important role in the formation of moral standards and human values. Through religious educational institutions, young people receive the necessary knowledge and education to grow into spiritually mature individuals.

Social activity: Uzbekistan pays great attention to the development of social activity. Various public organizations and non-governmental organizations are implementing various projects in order to attract young people to social life and ensure their spiritual development.

Spirituality is the intellectual potential of a person, morals, society and the state, and the educational power. We can learn this through the following criteria:

a set of requirements and rules that regulate social relations in society and interactions between people;

the system of spiritual values, customs, traditions, noble ideas and goals related to the life of the people and society;

a set of integrated spiritual phenomena consisting of ethics, culture, enlightenment, religion and educational system;

spiritual processes, creative activity of a person improving himself and the world he lives in;

human maturity, personal moral characteristics and educational qualities;

a sense of perfection and spiritual growth; through feelings such as material, spiritual, cultural and educational purification and elevation, one can see the spiritual image of a person in society [1:79].

The spiritual and educational activities of Uzbekistan are of great importance in the development of the country, in improving the spiritual state of our people and in preserving our cultural heritage. In order to further develop this activity, it is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the state, society and civil society. Through this, we can educate the younger generation as spiritually mature, morally strong individuals. In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5040 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work" dated March 26, 2021, in order to solve existing problems, increase the effectiveness and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, further expand its scope and scale, strengthen the sense of involvement in the reforms being implemented in the hearts of the country's population, primarily young people, and create a unified system for coordinating work in this area:[2:2-3]

The following are identified as priority areas for radically improving the system of spiritual and educational work:

to transform a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement in society by widely promoting the idea of "From National Revival to National Upliftment" based on the principles of goodness and humanity;

to ensure the continuity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods;

to organize work in the field of propaganda and education on a scientific basis, to increase the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in the field, and to introduce a permanent monitoring system aimed at strengthening the stability of the socio-spiritual environment;

to implement comprehensive measures aimed at eliminating such vices as indifference to the fate of the nation, localism, tribalism, corruption, disregard for family values, and irresponsibility for the upbringing of youth;

to increase the population's culture of using the Internet, to strengthen ideological immunity against ideological and information attacks;

to achieve the primacy of spiritual and moral criteria, national and universal values in all types of culture, literature, cinema, theater, music and art, publishing and printing products, and mass media;

to systematically study geopolitical and ideological processes, to conduct an effective ideological struggle against terrorism, extremism, fanaticism, human trafficking, drug trafficking and other dangerous threats, and to develop international cooperation in this regard.

As we see, in the current irreversible processes, time and history do not stand still, but if we do not immediately engage in the education of the younger generation, if we do not instill in their minds the values of our national culture and spiritual values, and if we do not popularize a healthy lifestyle, society will decline. To solve this problem, all individuals in society should fully understand the resolutions, decrees and laws issued by our President and government, namely, [3:97] the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy" signed on September 14, 2016, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further

Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, No. PF-5106 dated July 5, 2017 Decree “On increasing the effectiveness of state youth policy and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan”, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847 “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, Resolution No. PQ-3160 of July 28, 2017 “On increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the sector to a new level”, Resolution No. PQ-3775 of June 5, 2018 “On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the large-scale reforms being implemented in the country”, April 3, 2019 Resolution No. PQ-4307 “On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work”, Resolution No. 736 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 17, 2018 “On measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the education system”, Resolution No. 23 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 18, 2021 “On the implementation of state youth policy in Uzbekistan Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 310 dated June 7, 2022 “On approval of the Program for the implementation of state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2023” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 558 dated October 3, 2022 “On spiritual, educational and educational work in secondary educational institutions "On approval of the concept of increasing the efficiency of the National Security Service" and the implementation and fulfillment of the tasks set forth in the relevant regulatory and legal documents, the future generation will never go astray, but will contribute to the preservation and promotion of our national values and culture.

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